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**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

ProbeField

**A novel protocol for robust in field monitoring of
carbon stock and soil fertility based on proximal
sensors and existing soil spectral libraries**

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and Assessment by Soil Spectral Library Based
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ABSTRACT

The core of this protocol is a step-by-step guide for spectral sampling directly in the field and for the subsequent mathematical preprocessing of spectra to 1) reduce noise and enhance spectral features related to soil properties, and 2) remove moisture effects and align spectra with laboratory-based soil spectral libraries (SSLs). The reader is also introduced to the very basics of soil spectroscopy and the main results of the Horizon 2020 EJP SOIL ProbeField project that outlined and tested this protocol. One of the aims of the ProbeField project was to produce spectra sampled directly in the field that to the largest possible degree resemble laboratory spectra so that soil properties may be predicted by models calibrated on soil spectral libraries. By utilizing regional, national and multinational SSLs, already existing and under development, and at the same time minimizing efforts for collection, transport and preparation of soil samples, the full potential of soil Vis-NIR spectroscopy can be exploited. The protocol was tested on 180 locations in 7 countries involved in ProbeField. By correcting for moisture using External Parameter Orthogonalisation (EPO) and aligning data sets to each other through an Internal Soil Standard (ISS), prediction accuracy was in line with what can be expected from laboratory spectra of a similarly distributed data set.

The protocol summarizes a large part of the work carried out by the ProbeField partners representing: Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Aarhus University (AU), Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety Ltd. (AGES), Agroscope (AGS), University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU), National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU), National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE), Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation - State Research Institute (IUNG-PIB), General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM), University of Maribor, Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences (UM-FKBV) and Wageningen Environmental Research (WR).

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Vis-NIR(S)	Visible and Near Infrared (Spectroscopy)
EPO	External Parameter Orthogonalisation
SSL	Soil Spectral Library
CoDa	Compositional Data
SNV	Standard Normal Variate
DT	De-Trend
ISS	Internal Soil Standard
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SD	Standard Deviation
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
PCR	Principal Component Regression
PLS	Partial Least Squares Regression
SVM	Support Vector Machines

1. Introduction

The aim of this protocol is to demonstrate a workflow that allows to collect soil spectra in the visible to near infrared range (Vis-NIR) in the field with minimal preparation. These spectra shall subsequently be used to estimate soil properties by prediction models calibrated on soil spectral libraries (SSLs) that are based on laboratory spectra. By utilizing regional, national and multinational SSLs, already existing and under development, and at the same time minimize efforts for collection, transport and preparation of soil samples, the full potential of soil Vis-NIR spectroscopy can be exploited. The protocol is presented as a hands-on guide covering preparation and instrumentation for fieldwork, the collection of spectra in the field (section 3) and how to pre-process field and SSL spectra to reduce effects from moisture, structure and instrument differences (section 4). Thus, producing aligned data sets suitable for soil property estimation (section 5).

1.1. Target groups

Target groups for the present protocol are numerous. Service providers for agricultural land, management decision support and staff of governmental institutes that serve agricultural policy makers, who work with soil data are the most important target groups, but also the research community as a starting point for further development of field spectroscopy as well as the establishment of certified and accredited field spectroscopy routines and standards. The section demonstrating the field work (section 3) is particularly written for field staff with basic experience in Vis-NIR spectroscopy. The data management as described in sections 4 and 5 is not automatized and requires reasonable skills in spectroscopy and chemometrics. Experience in using “R”, “Phyton” or other data analysis tools is advantageous.

1.2. Areas of implementation

Vis-NIR spectroscopy is a fast, versatile and flexible acquisition system. The collection of a spectrum is a matter of seconds and the compatibility with fiber optics facilitates a diversity of sensor platforms and probes. Therefore, both high density point measurements and on-the-go measurements are supported. This protocol focuses on point measurements in agricultural soils. A multitude of purposes can be considered for rapid and cost-effective methods to assess soil characteristics as an alternative to wet chemistry analyses in the laboratory. Examples are monitoring, mapping and ground truthing or calibration for remote sensing approaches. Both the field scale for decision support in an agricultural context and the regional scale for monitoring are applications with large potentials.

1.3. Basic Vis-NIR soil spectroscopy

As the name implies, a full range Vis-NIR spectrophotometer produces spectra in the visible (~350-700 nm) and the near infrared (~700-2500 nm) region of the electromagnetic spectrum (Figure 1). Spectra are a display of the energy that is reflected by a sample subjected to a specified light source. The spectrum used is calculated as light reflected by the sample in relation to a standardized reference (usually a material that reflects close to 100% of the incoming radiation). The energy from the light source causes certain chemical bonds in the sample to vibrate and absorb energy. As different bonds require different amounts of energy to vibrate and different bands in the spectrum contain different amounts of energy, the composition of the sample will influence the shape of the reflectance

spectrum. In soil, features of minerals, especially clay minerals, organic matter and water absorb strongly in the Vis-NIR region.

Figure 1 Vis-NIR reflectance spectra. The reflectance is the proportion of light reflected from the sample in relation to the white reference (100% reflection). These example spectra originate from the same soil at five different moisture levels (5-30%) and the air dried sample (0%).

There is a range of manufacturers and types of instruments available. There are handheld instruments dedicated to field work with inbuilt light source and calibration features. Other instruments are portable but use an external sampling probe for contact measurements equipped with an internal light source attached to the instrument through fibre optics (Figure 2). A high-resolution instrument typically collects bands with a resolution of 2-10 nm.

1.4. Protocol background

The outlined protocol builds on experimentation and findings from the Horizon 2020 EJP SOIL (grant agreement 862695) project ProbeField “A novel protocol for robust in field monitoring of carbon stock and soil fertility based on proximal sensors and existing soil spectral libraries”. The consortium consisted of 14 partners in 12 European countries. Based on extensive literature studies and preliminary experiments we set up a field protocol for a range of procedures to collect good field spectra with as little deviation from laboratory spectra of sieved and dried soil as possible. Therefore, we investigated the main factors affecting the stability and the effectiveness of field spectra and then their capability to be used for soil property predictions. One of these factors was the soil surface roughness. In samples prepared for laboratory spectroscopy, structure is largely harmonized by sieving, while surfaces as they appear in the field can heavily affect the spectral responses, reducing the overall reflectance due to self-shadowing and light scattering between soil particles and aggregates. Another main disturbing factor for field spectroscopy is the soil moisture. The water in the soil seriously affects the spectral response, reducing the overall reflectance value (Figure 1). Increasing soil moisture content leads to a weakening of spectral features related to organic matter and soil minerals, as the water absorption bands broaden and tend to overlap and mask them. Therefore, high roughness and soil moisture lead to reduced accuracy in estimates. For this reason, we tested different soil surface pre-treatments for reducing soil roughness before the spectral acquisition and mathematical approaches for reducing the effect of soil moisture.

Figure 2 To the left a handheld full range Vis-NIR spectrophotometer and to the right two varieties of contact probes connected to a corresponding sensor via fiber optics.

1.4.1. Collecting field spectra

The field protocol specifies three different pre-treatments of the soil surface to be measured in the field. In seven countries with seven different spectrophotometers a total of 180 locations were sampled according to the three methods in the protocol. The three methods to be compared were:

The least possible treatment. This means that contaminating, non-soil, materials on the surface were removed and spectra were collected in five replicates from a 25x25 cm area avoiding stones, residues and cracks. In extreme cases, with for example algae growth on the surface, the very top layer was cut off with a flat spade.

Flattened surface. A surface like the one above was flattened and smoothed by light hammering on a board that was placed on the surface before sampling.

Cut core. A smooth surface cut with an auger or a spade down to 20 cm was sampled in five replicates distributed along the 20 cm.

1.4.2. Pre-processing spectra to remove moisture effects and align data sets

In a preliminary study, three frequently suggested methods to remove the moisture effect were tested. The External Parameter Orthogonalisation (EPO), the Direct Standardization and the Piecewise Direct Standardization methods were compared, and the EPO method was found to be most efficient in transforming spectra to make those originating from moist and dry soil correspond to each other (Figure 3). An EPO correction matrix was calculated by selecting 81 archive samples with high diversity and geographical distribution within Europe. Seven different spectrophotometers were used. Each sample was rewetted to five moisture classes, forming the basis for the correction matrix subsequently used on the collected field spectra.

Figure 3 Savitzky-Golay and D-trend processed spectra of the same soil at different moisture contents before and after moisture correction with the EPO transformation.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) content was the target soil property tested in our study. The calibration of prediction models was performed using the following three existing SSLs: The Mediterranean-focused Data hub GeoCradle (Regional Soil Spectral Library), the European LUCAS SSL (ESDAC, European Commission) and an SSL compiled by ProbeField partners (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13757028](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13757028)). Since the spectrophotometers used in the field were different from those used for the SSLs and different to each other, an internal soil standard was used to align spectra. In addition, standard procedures to manage noise, and to reduce scatter and structural effects were employed. Prediction models were calibrated and validated within the SSL used. Thus, prediction models were totally independent of the field spectra.

1.4.3. Main ProbeField findings

Typically, the treatment with a flattened surface performed best when predicted with laboratory-based SSL calibrations, indicating that a good contact between the sample and the sensor probe is of importance. The better performance of the flattened surface, as compared to the cut core, was attributed to the fact that spectra near the surface (flattened surface) tended to be dryer and spectra subsequently less affected by moisture.

Applying the lab-based SSL calibrations to the field spectra showed that using an ISS correction improved predictions to some extent while also correcting for moisture with EPO substantially improved the accuracy. Using the LUCAS SSL as the calibration dataset, we reduced the root mean squared error (RMSE) from 2.85% (using uncorrected spectra) to 0.94% (with EPO corrected spectra). The accuracy obtained using EPO-transformed field spectra was the same as that achieved by using spectral data acquired under laboratory conditions on the same soil samples. In addition, based on RMSE, the prediction performance of the field spectra was similar to what is commonly found from altogether laboratory based spectral data with similar standard deviations in SOC (Figure 4). This implies that the use of an internal soil standard and, more significantly, the moisture correction by EPO has allowed predictions of field spectra with a large-scale SSL with a precision equal to what could be expected after drying and sieving samples brought to the laboratory.

Figure 4 The ProbeField field spectra prediction performance with ISS and EPO in relation to SSL calibration with internal performance tests, published between 2000 and 2015. Three groups of calibration techniques are indicated by color. Statistics refer to the PLS group. RMSE is an indicator for inaccuracy as the average distance between measured and predicted and should preferably be low. The standard deviation refers to wet chemistry SOC in the predicted data set.

1.4.4. Compositional data analysis

Soil organic carbon content is a single component of soil constituents and considering the compositional nature of soil might improve its prediction. A composition is a data vector which elements are all soil constituents (components), which add up to a constant. The statistical analysis of compositional data sets is based on the idea that if all constituents in a soil sample are analysed, their concentrations sum up to a constant and the relationships that constituents have to one another are conditioned by the rest of the constituents included in the composition. For this purpose, SOC and the rest of the soil constituents would form a composition.

The compositional data (CoDa) analysis might in some way be thought of as an alternative approach to manage moisture effects by including water content as a soil component instead of a preceding spectral moisture correction. In the ProbeField project, CoDa was carried out to deal with soil moisture interference on Vis-NIR spectra for SOC prediction and the results indicated some improvements.

1.5. The decision tree concept

During the development of the protocol and the review of a broad range of proximal sensing techniques that can be used to measure soil properties in the field, the need for a decision support tool became evident to support users in choosing a strategy. The aim of such a tool is to allow users to

judge which proximal sensing application would be the appropriate choice for their needs based on applicability for their target area and the desired information. Applicability refers to spatial extent, or area of measurement, the platforms that can be used to measure the area, the needed measurement depth and the soil property to be estimated. In this first version we only focus on SOC. The suitability to answer the information needs of the user depends on the minimum accuracy and maximum cost, or the optimum between the two, that the survey should have. A higher accuracy or a lower cost is always desirable, but since there is usually a trade-off between the two, the optimum depends on the specified information needs. Information needs related questions a user might want to answer are for example: ‘How much does it cost me if I want to measure soil parameter X at regional scale with at least x% accuracy?’ or ‘Which is the best proximal sensing technique if I want to measure soil parameter Y on a field scale with the highest possible accuracy?’ or ‘I have Z amount of money and I’d like to measure at least soil parameter A for deriving management zones, but preferably I would also like to get information on soil parameter B, C and D to guide my land management in these zones. What should I use?’

To be able to cover the large variety of available sensors and platforms, as well as the wide range in different use cases or information requests, we propose a modular decision tree that allows different entry points and choices (spatial extent, soil parameter, platform, measurement depth etc.) and delivers an output table with accuracy (normalized RMSE) and cost information for the applicable sensing technique(s), ideally with a link to existing protocols (such as the present protocol for Vis-NIR).

2. Further reading

Below is a selection of overview articles and textbooks for a deeper understanding of Vis-NIR spectroscopy, soil spectroscopy in general, field spectroscopy and moisture corrections. Also, some suggestions are made for reading on chemometrics and multivariate calibration. All results produced within the ProbeField project are stored in Zenodo and can be found when searching for the keyword “ProbeField” ([Search results](#)).

Theoretical introduction to diffuse reflectance spectroscopy and chemometrics:

- Dahm, D.J. and Dahm, K. 2007. Interpreting Diffuse Reflectance and Transmittance: A Theoretical Introduction to Absorption Spectroscopy of Scattering Materials. IM Publications LLP. 286 pp.
- Near-Infrared Spectroscopy - Theory, Spectral Analysis, Instrumentation, and Applications. 2021. Ozaki, Y., Huck, C., Tsuchikawa, S. and Balling Engelsen, B. Springer, Singapore. 593 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-8648-4>

Soil Vis-NIR fundamentals:

- Stenberg, B., Viscarra Rossel, R. A., Mouazen, A. M., and Wetterlind, J. 2010. Visible and Near Infrared Spectroscopy in Soil Science. In "Advances in Agronomy" (L. S. Donald, ed.), Vol. Volume 107, pp. 163-215. Academic Press. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(10\)07005-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(10)07005-7)

Field spectroscopy:

- Piccini, C., Metzger, K., Debaene, G., Stenberg, B., Göttinger, S., Borůvka, L., Sandén, T., Bragazza, L., and Liebisch, F. 2024. In-field soil spectroscopy in Vis-NIR range for fast and

reliable soil analysis: A review. *European Journal of Soil Science* 75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13481>

- Metzger, K., Liebisch, F., Herrera, J.M., Guillaume, T., Walder, F., Bragazza, L. 2023. The use of visible and near-infrared spectroscopy for in situ characterization of agricultural soil fertility: a proposition of best practice by comparing scanning positions and spectrometers. *Soil Use and Management* 40(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12952>

Moisture correction:

- Knadel, M., Castaldi, F., Barbetti, R., Ben-Dor, E., Gholizadeh, A., and Lorenzetti, R. 2023. Mathematical techniques to remove moisture effects from visible-near-infrared-shortwave-infrared soil spectra-review. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews* 58, 629-662. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2022.2128365>

Calibration:

- Varmuza, K., Filzmoser, P. 2009. *Introduction to Multivariate Statistical Analysis in Chemometrics*. CRC Press, Boca Raton. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420059496>
- Wadoux, A.M.J.C., Malone, B., Minasny, B., Fajardo P, M., McBratney, A., 2021. *Soil Spectral Inference with R*. *Progress in Soil Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64896-1>

Compositional data:

- Pawlowsky-Glahn, V., Egozcue, J.J., Tolosana-Delgado, R. 2015. *Modelling and analysis of compositional data*. Statistics in practice. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester, UK. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119003144>
- Cayuela Sánchez, J. A., and López-Núñez, R. 2024. Report on compositional (CoDa) method to deals with soil moisture interference on VISNIR soil organic carbon measurement using the ProbeField sampleset of CSIC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13739635>

Decision tree development:

- Van Egmond, F., Liebisch, F., Metzger, K., Sandén, T., Koganti, T., Borůvka, L., Stenberg, B. 2024. Decision trees to assist soil sensing measurement choices. *Proceedings of the GPSS workshop 2024*.

Software:

- R package prospectr for spectral data management
 - Stevens, A., & Ramirez-Lopez, L. 2022. An introduction to the prospectr package, R package vignette R package version 0.2.6.
- Aspen Unscrambler™, www.aspentech.com.
 - Martens, H., and Naes, T. 1989. *Multivariate calibration*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK. 419 pp.

3. Field sampling

3.1. Suitable conditions for field measurements

Since soil properties are to be predicted on field sampled spectra by models calibrated on laboratory-based SLLs, the more field conditions and soil appearance resemble those in the lab, the better. For laboratory Vis-NIR spectroscopy the soil is typically sieved with 2 mm mesh, and dried.

- The soil should be as dry as possible. If it smears on boots, or the contact probe, it is too wet. [3.7.1. Note 1]
- A smooth homogenous surface without cracks, stones and residues should be strived for. [3.7.2. Note 2]
- The weather should be dry, above the freezing point and well within the temperature range specified for the instrument. [3.7.3. Note 3]
- The sampling point should be shadowed by clouds or a screen. [3.7.4. Note 4]

3.2. Sensor specification

This protocol is based on studies with full range Vis-NIR (~400-2500 nm) spectrophotometers with a sampling interval of 1-2 nm and band widths of 5-10 nm. The protocol as such will work for instruments with a more limited range or resolution if the SSL spectra are adjusted accordingly. However, to what extent the calibration performance will be affected is beyond the scope of this protocol.

3.3. Meta data

For each data point register:

- Coordinates.
- Weather situation, including air temperature and cloudiness. If possible, also the temperature of the measured soil surface (IR-thermometer).
- Vegetation.
- Soil surface conditions (for example: degree of open soil, surface structure, residue cover, algae, mosses, stoniness, apparent dryness).

3.4. Equipment for soil preparation

- A flat spade, for example an edging spade, a hand spade, a suitable knife, or any tool to cut a thin layer of the soil surface off.
- A rubber or wooden mallet of approximately 1 kg.
- A resistant and sturdy 25 x 25 cm board or block with a flat smooth surface.

Figure 5 From left to right: A soil surface in smooth and homogenous condition; A surface contaminated with residues and algae, depicting also some cracks (orange area is the sensor light beam); A surface with hard clods and cracks not allowing good contact with the probe.

3.5. Sensor setup

As the different brands and models of spectrometers require different setup and handling steps, please refer to the instrument manual, but in general ensure sufficient warming up of the instruments. Regular calibration to the white or grey (instrument dependent) reference is important. Especially outdoors, where conditions constantly change. Consider calibration more frequently in the beginning as the warming up period likely will suffer during field work. If the spectra are used together with spectra from other spectrometers it is necessary to regularly collect spectra from an Internal Soil Standard (ISS) to allow for the subsequent instrument alignment in section 4.4.

3.6. Soil preparation and collection of spectra

There are two main alternatives depending on the condition of the soil surface.

- 1) If the raw surface without pretreatment is in good condition, that is relatively smooth and homogenous, without residues or other non-soil contamination (Figure 5):
 - Take 5 replicate scans in an area of 25 x 25 cm.
 - Avoid obvious stones and organic residues.
 - Select areas allowing good contact between soil and probe.

1.b) If the surface is too uneven, but otherwise in good condition (Figure 5):

- Remove surface stones.
- Put the 25 x 25 cm board on the surface.

- Hammer on the board with the mallet.
 - Do not use too much force so that water is squeezed to the surface.
 - Take 5 replicate scans in the 25 x 25 cm area.
 - Avoid obvious stones and residues.
 - Select areas allowing good contact between soil and probe.
- 2) If the surface is covered with residues or is old and contaminated (Figure 5):
- Cut a thin slice of the surface off with a flat spade or knife to produce a fresh surface.
 - The thinner the slice, the less soil moisture content will increase.
 - Take 5 replicate scans in an area of 25 x 25 cm.
 - Avoid obvious stones and organic residues.
 - Select areas allowing good contact between soil and probe.
- 2.b) If the surface is too uneven (Figure 5):
- Remove surface stones.
 - Put the 25 x 25 cm board on the newly cut surface.
 - Hammer on the board with the mallet.
 - Do not use too much force so that water is squeezed to the surface.
 - Take 5 replicate scans in the 25 x 25 cm area.
 - Avoid obvious stones and organic residues.
 - Select areas allowing good contact between soil and probe.

3.7. Notes

3.7.1. Note 1

Vis-NIR spectra are strongly influenced by water and if too moist or wet, crucial soil information will be masked. In section 4.5 it is described how to correct spectra for moisture effects and artefacts, but the rule of thumb is: the dryer the better. In practice this means that after a rainfall or irrigation event enough time should have passed for water to drain off and the soil to dry up at least until it can be comfortably walked upon without smearing.

3.7.2. Note 2

To collect a good spectrum with a high signal to noise ratio, good contact between the probe and the soil is important. Cracks and very coarse or uneven surfaces must be avoided. Within a couple of weeks after seed bed preparation is presumably an example of a good measurement window.

3.7.3. Note 3

The temperature range of the instrument given by the manufacturer should not be violated. The soil must not be frozen. Cold and moist weather may cause mist on the probe and should be avoided.

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3.7.4. Note 4

Spectral quality is negatively influenced by stray light. To minimize this effect direct sunlight should be avoided. A cloudy day or arranged shadow for the sampling point is advantageous to avoid stray light artefacts.

4. Data preprocessing

Once the soil spectra have been acquired in the field (or in the laboratory), the spectral data need to be processed before being used for further applications and computations. Whether original spectral data is expressed in reflectance or absorbance, the spectral pre-processing could include all steps listed below but can also be reduced if spectral quality allows. This will depend on factors such as type of spectrometer, spectral resolution (range, number of bands, bandwidths), spectral noise and the environmental conditions at the time of the spectral measurements. The preprocessing steps are proposed here in a time sequence from raw, out of the instrument spectra, to ready to use for interpretation. It is important that the calibration and validation or prediction sets are processed according to the same procedure. Several software for preprocessing spectral data exists. Here, we provide information on the packages and functions that can be used in the R environment.

4.1. Removing/reducing sensor artefacts and noise

4.1.1. Correction for sensor gaps between detectors

A spectral correction is needed for spectral artifacts manifesting as steps due to sensor gaps between adjacent regions covered by two or more detectors.

- The *spliceCorrection* function in the *prospectr* package in R software (10.32614/CRAN.package.prospectr) uses linear interpolation for smoothing the signal. [4.5.1. Note 1]

4.1.2. Removal of noisy spectral edges

- Remove edge wavelength regions at about 350-400 nm and 2450-2500 nm that are usually affected by low signal-to-noise ratios of the instruments.

4.1.3. Spectral smoothing

Spectral smoothing is advisable to reduce noise in spectra, and its magnitude depends on the detectable noise level and the spectral resolution.

- The goal is a good trade-off between noise reduction and loss of spectral features.
- It is common practice to use moving window average or Savitzky-Golay (second order polynomial and a window size of 11 bands is suggested as a starting point, but may be instrument dependent) filters for smoothing spectra.
- In R the *savitzkyGolay()* function of the *prospectr* package can be used (10.32614/CRAN.package.prospectr).

4.2. Spectral outliers' management

An outlier spectrum is a spectrum that is significantly distant (dissimilar) from the population of spectra, due to a measurement error or caused by heterogeneity of the material under investigation.

- For spectrometers that allow to visualize the spectra during their collection in the field or in the lab, the visual check can be sufficient to avoid out of the ordinary measurements, allowing for immediate re-sampling.
- The quality of replicated measurements can be checked by calculating an index:
 - Calculate the standard deviation of the replicates for each wavelength (calculated on a reflectance range of 0-1, quotient, not percentage, of the white or grey reference).
 - Calculate the standard deviation of the deviations along each spectrum. If the final value is <0.01 the spectra are ok, if the value is above >0.01 the replicates need to be checked visually and eventually removed (the threshold of 0.01 may need to be increased for heterogeneous materials).
 - Then the average reflectance of each band of the remaining spectra are calculated resulting in the average spectrum.
 - All subsequent spectral processing will be done on the average spectrum of the filtered replicated measurements.

4.3. Spectral transformation

The objective of spectral transformation is to improve the quality of spectra by removing unwanted variations before modelling. Common transformations typically correct for baseline and albedo differences or enhance spectral features of the material. Thereby sample structure effects on spectra are reduced.

There are several transformations available. The following three are commonly used (Figure 6 [Note 2]):

- Standard normal variate (SNV): removes scatter effects by centring and scaling individual spectra. SNV is often used in combination with De-trending (DT), which removes overall trends and curvature of spectra. The *standardNormalVariate()* function of the *prospectr* package in R can be used for this purpose combining SNV and de-trending (SNV-DT). The first or second-order derivatives highlight subtle features within spectra. Both first- and second order derivatives remove the baseline while the latter transformation eliminates the linear trend of each spectrum, too.
- Continuum removal transformation performs an albedo normalization that allows to highlight energy absorption features of the main soil properties but is sensitive to start and end point noise in the spectra. The *continuumRemoval()* function of the *prospectr* package in R can be used for this purpose.

Figure 6 The effect of SNV-DT and Continuum removal on reflectance soil spectra.

4.4. Spectral alignment/harmonization

To merge spectral data acquired by different instruments and origins in a single and harmonized soil spectral library (SSL), it is advised to carry out a re-alignment procedure by using an internal soil standard (ISS). The best documented and tested ISS is the Lucky Bay (LB) being dune sand (99% quartz) from Australia. [Note 3]

- The ISS should have been scanned at least at the beginning of each field measurement session but ideally also afterwards or in terms of long campaigns in-between.
- The field spectra will be corrected by multiplying each band with a correction factor (CF) computed according to the following formula:

$$CF_i = 1 - \frac{S_{i\lambda} - M_\lambda}{S_{i\lambda}}$$

Where $S_{i\lambda}$ is the ISS reflectance measured using the i instrument for each band/wavelength (λ) and M_λ is the ISS reflectance acquired at the CSIRO laboratory (benchmark spectrum).

4.5. Soil moisture removal

The External Parameter Orthogonalization (EPO) is one of the most efficient mathematical algorithms for removing soil moisture effects from field soil spectra (Figure 3, [Note 4]).

- To apply EPO to field spectra, we need to multiply them by a correction matrix computed from the differences between dry and wet spectra acquired from sub samples of the same soil samples (see section 2).
- This matrix can be built within one's own laboratory by scanning many soil samples at different soil moisture levels or the ProbeField EPO matrix can be used (<https://zenodo.org/records/13753159>).

4.5.1. Note 1

Most of the (Vis-NIR; 400-2500 nm) spectrometers, both those made for field and lab measurements, are composed of two or three detectors covering adjacent spectral regions. In these regions we can visually detect spectral artifacts, as steps, that could affect the proceeding mathematical analysis. Therefore, if evident steps can be noticed at splice wavelengths, a spectral correction is needed. The *prospectr* R package can be used for correcting ASD artifacts by the function *spliceCorrection* that uses linear interpolation for smoothing the signal.

4.5.2. Note 2

The objective of spectral transformation (pre-processing) is to improve the quality of spectra by removing unwanted variations before modelling. There are several transformations available in addition to these three, but for soil these are the most frequently used (see section 2).

4.5.3. Note 3

As an alternative to the ISS approach, model (or calibration) transfer has been developed to implement the previously calibrated models from one measurement setting to another. Model transfer is commonly employed to transfer a model constructed on the master (source) instrument to a target instrument. Model transfer techniques can be categorized into two different approaches. One includes the direct standardization (DS), piecewise direct standardization (PDS) and repeatability file (Repfile), which transform the benchmark and user's setup spectra matrices. The other approach to the model transfer consists of techniques such as model updating, bias/slope correction (BSC) and transfer by orthogonal projection (TOP).

4.6. Note 4

The External Parameter Orthogonalization (EPO) is one of the most efficient mathematical algorithms for removing soil moisture effects from field soil spectra. To apply EPO to field spectra, we need to multiply them by a correction matrix computed from the differences between dry and wet spectra acquired for the same soil samples.

5. Soil property estimation

Direct quantitative prediction of soil properties from soil diffuse reflectance spectra is challenging because individual absorption features are often difficult to identify in the Vis-NIR spectra as they are largely non-specific and overlap. Exploring spectral data in multivariate space is required to extract useful information from spectral data and to relate them to wet chemistry or physical properties by empirical models. Calibration models are designed to predict the soil properties of interest from Vis-NIR spectra. There are no theoretically based mathematical equations for the relation between the soil properties (dependent data) and the spectra (independent data). The development of techniques for calibration is in continuous progress. It is not possible to say that one method is better than another. It largely depends on the data. The approach in this protocol has SSLs as a starting point. SSLs are per definition large and diverse. This suggests that the more complex and sophisticated calibration methods can be considered. It is, however, outside the scope of this protocol to give an overview of possibilities and we refer to section 2 and a vast scientific literature on the subject for further information.

